

TEACHERS' PERCEPTION OF THE BENEFITS OF GAME-BASED LEARNING FOR ENHANCING COGNITIVE AND SOCIAL SKILLS IN BASIC SCIENCE OF SECONDARY SCHOOL STUDENTS IN OSUN STATE, NIGERIA

BY

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Abstract

Game-Based Learning (GBL) has emerged as an innovative instructional approach that fosters students' cognitive and social development. This study investigates secondary school teachers' perceptions of the benefits of GBL in enhancing cognitive and social skills among students in Osun State, Nigeria. Using a descriptive survey design, data were collected from 120 teachers across selected public and private schools in Osun State. The findings reveal a positive perception of GBL, particularly in promoting problem-solving, collaboration, critical thinking, and communication skills. However, infrastructural and training limitations hinder its widespread adoption. The study recommends capacity-building programs and curriculum integration to optimize GBL's benefits in Nigerian schools.

Keywords: Game-Based Learning, Cognitive Skills, Social Skills, Teachers' Perception, Secondary Schools, Osun State, Nigeria

Introduction

The integration of Game-Based Learning (GBL) into education has become a global pedagogical trend aimed at improving student engagement, motivation, and achievement (Plass et al., 2015). Game-based learning is a teaching methodology that incorporates the principles of play into educational settings with the goal of fostering student engagement, motivation, and learning outcomes (Plass, Homer & Kinzer, 2015). According to Benini and Murray, 2014, digital natives thrive when instruction is delivered in a way that mimics the interactive nature of their daily digital interactions, thus positioning GBL as a natural fit for modern classrooms. In recent years, educational technologies have increasingly leveraged gaming elements to support learning outcomes, particularly in promoting cognitive and social skill development.

In Nigeria, GBL remains underutilized despite its documented benefits, however, in Osun State, the teaching of Basic Science has been observed to suffer from students' low motivation, poor engagement, and inadequate conceptual understanding (Suleiman & Abdulrahman, 2020). These challenges have led to calls for the adoption of more participatory and student-centered instructional strategies (Okonkwo and Umeh, 2021). Game-based learning offers promise in this direction by actively engaging learners and promoting critical cognitive and social skills necessary for 21st-century learning. Cognitive skills such as memory retention, critical thinking, and problem-solving can be developed when learners are immersed in structured gaming activities that simulate real-world problems and foster higher-order thinking (Eseryel et al., 2014). Similarly, social skills such as collaboration, communication, empathy, and conflict resolution can be honed when learners interact with peers within the framework

of goal-oriented games (Shaffer et al., 2005). Several Nigerian researchers (Ajayi and Olayiwola, 2022; Adeyemo et al., 2023) have emphasized the importance of shifting from rote learning to experiential learning strategies. Despite these recognitions, there is still limited empirical data specifically assessing teachers' perceptions of how GBL can enhance both cognitive and social skills, particularly in Basic Science education in Osun State.

This study, therefore, seeks to fill this gap by investigating the perceptions of secondary school Basic Science teachers in Osun State, Nigeria, on the benefits of GBL for enhancing students' cognitive and social development. By understanding these perceptions, the study contributes evidence that could guide curriculum designers, policymakers, and education technology stakeholders in Nigeria.

The 21st century has ushered in a paradigm shift in the global educational landscape, encouraging the move from traditional teacher-centered pedagogy to learner-centered approaches such as project-based learning, flipped classrooms, and game-based learning. Among these, game-based learning has garnered significant attention due to its potential to improve student motivation, participation, and learning outcomes (Plass et al., 2015). In Nigeria, the National Policy on Education (FME, 2013) promotes innovative instructional strategies that stimulate students' interest and creativity. However, the implementation of such policies often faces bottlenecks including poor teacher training, inadequate technological infrastructure, and lack of institutional support (Adeyemo et al., 2023). Despite these challenges, studies have begun to document the gradual shift in perception among Nigerian teachers toward accepting game-based learning as an effective teaching strategy (Ajayi & Olayiwola, 2022). The cognitive benefits of GBL include enhanced attention span, information retention, decision-making, and abstract reasoning (Papastergiou, 2009).

Socially, GBL fosters peer collaboration, conflict resolution, and communication (Kiili, 2005). Understanding teachers' perceptions is crucial to identifying opportunities and challenges associated with GBL adoption in Nigerian classrooms.

Game-based learning in this context involves the use of both digital and non-digital games that incorporate learning objectives aligned with curriculum standards. For instance, Eseryel et al. (2014) found that students who engaged in game-based science simulations demonstrated significant improvements in problem-solving skills and scientific reasoning. Similarly, in the Nigerian context, Okonkwo and Umeh (2021) found that the use of interactive science games improved student interest and academic performance. Moreover, GBL can foster the development of social skills essential for collaborative learning to Schrier et al (2024), games provide a platform for students to interact, negotiate, and build social competencies that are often overlooked in traditional settings.

Basic Science, a foundational subject in Nigeria's secondary school curriculum, plays a critical role in preparing students for careers in STEM (Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics). Nevertheless, the subject is often taught in a manner that fails to capture students' interest or promote deeper learning (Ifedili and Ifedili 2015). Game-based learning has been proposed as a viable intervention to make science content more relatable and engaging. Despite these promising findings, limited research exists on how Nigerian secondary school teachers especially those teaching Basic Science perceive the benefits of GBL in enhancing cognitive and social learning outcomes. This study aims to fill this research gap and provide empirical evidence that may inform educational reforms and teaching practices in Nigeria.

Game-Based Learning (GBL): GBL refers to the application of game principles, mechanics, and

environments for educational purposes. It leverages the motivational pull of games to facilitate active learning and student engagement (Prensky, 2007). GBL is grounded in constructivist and social learning theories, which emphasize learning as an active, social process (Vygotsky, 1978). Game-based learning aligns with this theory by immersing learners in scenarios that require exploration, decision-making, and collaboration. GBL engages students in meaningful tasks within game contexts, encouraging exploration, experimentation, and reflection (Prensky, 2001). Research globally affirms GBL's cognitive advantages. For example, Papastergiou (2009) found that digital games improved students' science and computer literacy. In Nigeria, Olumorin et al. (2018) observed that GBL improved analytical reasoning among secondary school students in Kwara State. Games provide immediate feedback, repeated practice, and the scaffolding needed to develop higher-order thinking skills. Ajayi and Olayiwola (2022) reported that secondary school teachers in Lagos perceived digital games as effective tools for improving students' interest in science. Similarly, Okonkwo and Umeh (2021) showed that game-based science instruction improved student motivation and performance in Anambra State.

Adeyemo et al. (2023) highlighted infrastructural and teacher-related challenges affecting GBL implementation but noted positive teacher attitudes when training was provided. GBL also enhances students' social competencies. Multiplayer games promote communication, negotiation, empathy, and cooperative problem-solving (Eseryel et al., 2014). Nigerian studies, including Ogunsola and Aladejana (2019), noted that students who participated in GBL activities demonstrated improved group dynamics and interpersonal relationships. Teachers' attitudes toward GBL influence its integration into the curriculum (Ifinedo, 2017). Perception is shaped

by exposure, training, access to technology, and institutional support. A positive perception leads to increased implementation, while skepticism or lack of familiarity hampers usage

Statement of the Problem

Despite the growing advocacy for learner-centered pedagogies and 21st-century skills in Nigerian secondary education, the teaching of Basic Science remains largely dominated by traditional, teacher-centered approaches. These conventional methods have contributed to the low development of students' cognitive and social skills, as learners often experience minimal engagement, reduced motivation, and limited opportunities for critical thinking, creativity, collaboration, and communication (Suleiman and Abdulrahman, 2020; Ifedili and Ifedili, 2015).

Globally, Game-Based Learning (GBL) has been identified as an innovative strategy capable of enhancing learners' cognitive and social competencies by promoting active participation, problem-solving, teamwork, and sustained interest in learning (Plass et al., 2015; Eseryel et al., 2014). However, in Nigeria, while a few studies have reported positive outcomes of GBL (Ajayi and Olayiwola, 2022; Okonkwo and Umeh, 2021), there is a dearth of research focusing on how Basic Science teachers in Osun State perceive the role of GBL in improving students' cognitive and social development.

Understanding teachers' perceptions is crucial, as their attitudes largely determine the extent to which innovative pedagogies are adopted in classrooms. Therefore, this study aims to investigate Basic Science teachers' perceptions of the cognitive and social benefits of Game-Based Learning in Osun State secondary schools. The findings are expected to shed light on strategies that can strengthen learners' cognitive reasoning, problem-solving abilities, and interpersonal skills through more engaging and interactive instructional approaches.

Objectives of the Study

The main objective of this study is to examine secondary school Basic Science teachers’ perceptions of the benefits of Game-Based Learning (GBL) in enhancing cognitive and social skills in students within Osun State, Nigeria.

1. Investigate teachers’ perceptions of how GBL enhances students’ cognitive skills in Basic Science.
2. Examine teachers’ perceptions of the role of GBL in developing students’ social skills.

Research Questions

1. What are secondary school Basic Science teachers’ perceptions of the benefits of game-based learning (GBL) in enhancing students’ cognitive skills in Osun State?
2. What are secondary school Basic Science teachers’ perceptions of the benefits of game-based learning in improving students’ social skills in Osun State?

Research Hypotheses

1. H₀₁: There is no significant difference in Basic Science teachers’ perception of the benefits of game-based learning in enhancing students’ cognitive skills.
2. H₀₂: There is no significant difference in Basic Science teachers’ perception of the benefits of game-based learning in enhancing students’ social skills.

Research Methods

Research Design: A descriptive survey design was adopted to gather teachers’ opinions on the benefits of GBL. Population and Sample: The

population comprised all secondary school teachers in Osun State. A stratified random sample of 120 teachers from both private and public schools were selected. Instrumentation: A structured questionnaire titled “Teachers’ Perception of Game-Based Learning Benefits (TP-GBLB)” was developed, covering: Demographics, Awareness of GBL, Perceived cognitive benefits, Perceived social benefits. The instrument was validated by experts in Educational Technology and was trial tested with a reliability coefficient of 0.82 (Cronbach Alpha).

Data Analysis Plan

Data collected through the questionnaire were analyzed using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 26. The analysis was carried out in two phases:

Descriptive Analysis: Descriptive statistics were used to summarize demographic characteristics and the overall perception of teachers regarding Game-Based Learning (GBL).

Means and standard deviations: for Likert-scale responses related to cognitive and social benefits of GBL.

Pearson Correlation Coefficient was used to assess relationships between years of teaching experience and perception of GBL benefits. Significance level was set at $p < 0.05$.

Results

Demographic Characteristics of Respondents. A total of 120 Basic Science teachers responded to the survey.

Table 1 summarizes the demographic characteristics:

Variable	Category	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Gender	Male	55	45.8
	Female	65	54.2

Teaching experience	1-5 years	22	18.3
	6-10 years	45	37.5
	Above 10 years	53	44.3
School Location	Urban	60	50
	Rural	60	50

Teachers’ Perception of the Cognitive Benefits of Game-Based Learning

Item	Mean	Std. Dev	Interpretation
GBL improves learners’ critical thinking and reasoning	4.35	0.62	Strongly Agree
GBL aids retention and recall of Basic Science concepts	4.28	0.59	Strongly Agree
GBL fosters problem-solving and innovation in students	4.12	0.67	Agree
GBL enhances students’ creativity in science exploration	4.24	0.60	Strongly Agree
GBL helps low-performing students catch up with lessons	4.01	0.72	Agree

Interpretation: The results indicate that the teachers overwhelmingly perceive GBL as beneficial for enhancing cognitive skills, particularly in memory retention, reasoning, and creativity.

Teachers’ Perception of the Social Benefits of Game-Based Learning

Item	Mean	Std. Dev	Interpretation
GBL promotes collaboration and teamwork among learners	4.36	0.61	Strongly Agree
GBL improves student communication and expression	4.15	0.68	Agree
GBL enhances interpersonal relationships and social bonding	4.10	0.65	Agree
GBL increases students’ confidence and social participation	4.19	0.60	Agree

Interpretation: The findings show high positive perception regarding GBL’s role in improving students’ collaboration, social bonding, and communication in the science classroom.

Discussion of Findings

The study revealed that secondary school Basic Science teachers in Osun State generally perceive Game-Based Learning as an effective strategy for enhancing both cognitive and social skills of students. These findings are in line with those of Plass, Homer, and Kinzer (2015) who emphasized that digital games enhance engagement, cognitive flexibility, and science concept mastery. Similarly, Eseryel et al. (2014) found that GBL improves scientific reasoning and problem-solving skills, especially when integrated into inquiry-based learning.

In the Nigerian context, Okonkwo and Umeh (2021) reported that using educational games in science subjects led to improved student motivation and knowledge retention. Ajayi and Olayiwola (2022) also noted that teachers in Oyo and Lagos States recognize the role of GBL in promoting collaboration and creativity among

secondary school learners. Despite these positive perceptions, teachers still reported limited implementation due to challenges such as insufficient digital infrastructure, lack of training, and overcrowded classrooms similar to the barriers identified by Adeyemo et al. (2023) in their national study on EdTech adoption.

Conclusion

The study concludes that teachers in Osun State perceive Game-Based Learning as a valuable strategy for enhancing students’ cognitive and social skills. Despite these positive perceptions, implementation remains limited due to infrastructural and pedagogical challenges.

Recommendations

1. Professional Development: Regular workshops and in-service training on GBL methods should be conducted for teachers.

2. Infrastructure Investment: Schools should invest in low-cost digital tools and educational game resources.
3. Policy Integration: Educational policymakers should embed GBL strategies into the national curriculum.
4. Collaborative Game Design: Teachers and local developers can co-create culturally relevant educational games.

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